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METHODOLOGICAL ADVANCEMENTS IN THE ENGLISH INSTRUCTION OF PRESCHOOLERS

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Abstract: This article provides information on the methods of teaching English to preschool children. Also, this article gives ideas about the advantages and effective methods of learning English at preschool age.

Key words: methods, preschoolers, games, songs, visual diagrams.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga ingliz tilini o'rgatish usullari haqida ma'lumot berilgan. Shuningdek, ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar uchun ingliz tilini o'rganishning afzalliklari va samarali usullari haqida fikrlar mavjud.

Kalit so'zlar: usullar, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar, o'yinlar, qo'shiqlar, vizual diagrammalar.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена информация о методах преподавания английского языка детям дошкольного возраста. Также размышляются о преимуществах и эффективных методах изучения английского языка в дошкольном возрасте.

Ключевые слова: методика, дошкольники, игры, песни, наглядные схемы.

INTRODUCTION

Language acquisition is often a natural process that occurs with the inputs of individuals while engaging with the people around them, requiring no extra effort until a certain age. Linguistic learning entails the deliberate formation of linguistic norms, systems, and patterns. Learning and applying information in a new language is an intentional and effort-required process. Foreign language training in early infancy has been a hot subject all around the world in recent years. The emphasis on preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan may be seen in the following orders and decrees. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan № DRU–595 of December 16, 2019 “On Preschool Education and Training”, the Law of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan №PD–4947 of February 7, 2017 “On the Republic of Uzbekistan Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan №. PD–2707 of December 29, 2016 “On measures to further improve the preschool education system in 2017–2021”, dated September 9, 2017 №PD–3261 “On measures to fundamentally improve the preschool education system”, №PD–3289 dated September 26, 2017 “Training of pedagogic personnel, public “On measures to further improve the system of education and training of education workers”, № PD–4312 of May 8, 2019 “Approving the concept of development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 Cabinet of Ministers Resolution № 1026 of December 28, 2017 “On measures to organize the retraining of pedagogues and their professional development”, № 391 of May 13, 2019 “Preschool educational institutions “Decision on measures to further improve the activity”.

There are several points of view on foreign language instruction in preschool education establishments. According to one point of view, humans have a flexible brain structure throughout the time from infancy to adolescence, and this flexibility decreases with age, hence it is better to begin foreign language education from a young age. Another point of view is that youngsters are hardwired to acquire languages and absorb what they hear. On the other side, a group of experts believed that teaching foreign languages to children at a young age would have a negative impact on their cognitive development and that language acquisition processes would be slowed owing to disruptions in the children's mother tongue. These recommendations demonstrate that there is no one, all-inclusive theoretical paradigm for foreign language education in early infancy, nor is there a single approach that covers all learners. From the past to the present, each new approach is often designed

to compensate for the deficiencies of the preceding one or to cover the gaps where it is inadequate. One of the most essential problems raised by educators is how to teach a foreign language, which theory to apply, and which method to utilize. Because each kid differs in terms of developmental traits, requirements, motivation, and learning style, there is no one correct approach in foreign language teaching; hence, several diverse teaching methods are synthesized and employed together in foreign language teaching.

How to Teach English to Young Learners. It takes a lot of care and ingenuity to prepare children's minds to absorb the glories of English. If you've attended language classes as a youngster and as an adult, you'll realize how different your lessons may be. Knowing how to teach English to young learners is an entirely different matter.

While filling down verb conjugation tables twenty times over is an excellent learning approach for adults, first graders will be hard pushed to stay still long enough to do the same. Similarly, urging your business English class of professionals and university students to sit in a circle and clap along to a colour song will raise many eyebrows. Good luck convincing a 50-year-old businessman to play Simon Says!

It might be challenging to keep your young students attention for a full class. However, you may make the most of your energy and interest. Here's how to teach English to kids with fun games and activities!

1. Turn lessons into songs

Every English learner, both native and not, is familiar with, at the very least, one classic jingle. Yes, the ABCs are what we turn to for a reminder of what letter comes after Q. Although the middle part requires a bit more brain power, the song offers English speakers a comfortable reference point for all their alphabetical needs.

Turning vocab, grammar, and dialogues into catchy tunes is a fabulous method for teaching English to young learners. If you're reviewing common material, try turning to YouTube to see if there's already a suitable song out there. Otherwise, you can hone your inner Beethoven to compose a musical masterpiece using the tune of another easy song, such as Twinkle Twinkle Little Star.

2. Create visual diagrams to illustrate new vocabulary

Head, shoulders, knees, and toes. These are a whole lot easier to point out on a smiling stick man than to write out in a vocabulary list. Visual devices provide a double whammy, too. Students can enjoy coloring or even adding on to pictures, while also absorbing what the new words they are learning look like.

Highlighting, underlining, and circling are all common visual tricks adults use to recall snippets of information. Creating visual diagrams is the same basic idea, so that the little ones can start to visualize what English looks like. As a bonus, students can more easily locate learning aids with distinct colors and illustrations among their folders of messy papers.

3. Encourage mnemonic devices to memorize grammar rules

Please Excuse My Dear Aunt Sally, or PEMDAS, is a popular mnemonic device for recalling the order of operations in math. When it comes to teaching English to children, memory aids make it easier to remember hard-to-spell words or complex grammar points. Whether that means creating a mnemonic device in students' native languages or breaking it down into simpler English words, the goal remains the same: better memory!

A useful mnemonic for all levels of English learners is "-i before -e, except after c". Once you can get your students to recite that phrase on command, expect those pesky i/e spelling mistakes to poof away! (If all else fails, turn to essential ESL resources to gain even more insight on how to teach English to children.)

4. Weave in spontaneous or consistent dialogues throughout the lesson

What did you do this weekend? By kicking off class with an expected question, you can get your students thinking about what they'll say long before class even starts. Natural dialogue also introduces students to everyday vocabulary relevant to their own lives and interests.

If you're working with a class, rather than a single student, you can also sprinkle in some side conversations with students as they work diligently on differentiating between I and me. Ask what's for lunch, how the last soccer game went, or anything at all that gets them excited to share!

5. Break up solitary study sessions with games

Ah, the holy grail of how to teach English to young learners – games.

Childhood education without games is like chicken wings without seasoning or sauce. You simply can't have one without the other. Games are especially effective teaching methods for young learners because kids are able to learn without realizing it. Active games let them expel some bottled up energy and quiet ones challenge and require concentration.

6. What are some games to try? Think of some you played as a kid!

Think theater class with an English twist. Picking up the role of a police officer or elderly neighbor on the spot can be intimidating to any aged student. However, if you have some fun with it and create a more relaxed expectation for students to act out roles, they'll be less stressed about making mistakes.

After all, teaching English to children should be about building up speaking confidence and a solid foundation. The perfect subject-verb-agreement and conjugations can be fine-tuned later!

Pick up some wacky wigs, sunglasses, and hats to help students step into character and feel more like they're acting, not just presenting a dialogue. Once they really embrace their character, you might be shocked to find just how creative the little Shakespeare's can get with their new vocabulary!

7. Repeat previous lessons in every class

Assuming the average class duration is only an hour or less, that leaves a whole lot of time in the day to forget everything a student just learned. Children won't retain as much information as adults, so repetition is key in English for young learners.

Rather than calling case closed at the end of a lesson and moving on after a test, be sure to pack every class with tons of repetition from lessons before. This also helps students to use vocabulary and grammar points all together, rather than depend on the same example sentences and templates they learn isolated in each lesson.

8. Get out of the classroom!

If you're a first-time English teacher, the idea of leading kids out into the big, wide world and outside the safe classroom walls may sound like a disaster waiting to happen. But if you're teaching English to young learners in-person and have permission to do so, take the kiddos out on a stroll. The change in scenery opens up a whole new box of situations to practice new vocabulary in its natural habitat

Conclusion:

Teaching English to young learners will be fun! You may utilize the same entertaining teaching strategies whether you teach ESL online or in person, but slightly modified. For example, if you teach via webcam, you may still encourage your students to play hangman and other writing games using their own little whiteboard or pen and paper. Do you have any flash cards or memory games? Your student can utilize the internet to watch your shared screen or work on a game you made with parental supervision and approval.

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